

Initiatives and Challenges for Small and Medium Entrepreneurs

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Abstract

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a pivotal role in the economic and social development of India. The MSME sector contributes to the manufacturing output, employment and exports. It plays a key role in the development of the economy with their effective, efficient, flexible and innovative entrepreneurial spirit. MSMEs contribute 45% to the industrial output, 40% of exports, employing 60 million people, create 1.3 million jobs every year. It produces more than 8,000 quality products for the Indian and international markets. Its contribution to GDP in 2011 was 17% which increased to 22% in 2012.

Introduction

MSME are the engines of growth of any country’s economy. By the provision of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Development Act 2006 the micro, small and medium enterprises are classified into two classes, Namely 1. Manufacturing enterprises and 2. Service Enterprises. MSME sector has emerged as a dynamic and vibrant sector of the economy. It is expected that the Indian economy will grow by over 8% per annum until 2020. The major advantage of this sector is its generating employment at low cost. But there are various problems faced by these enterprises due to which the growth of the enterprises is affected, in turn affecting the growth of the country.

Objectives of the Study

- To study and examine MSME role in India.
- To study issues and challenges faced by SME’s in India.
- To develop a review of the literature matrix model.
- To Construct a conceptual model linking issues and challenges.

Methodology

The study involves a critical analysis of functioning of some micro, small and medium scale enterprises in the country both in manufacturing and service sector and intends to identify the potentialities for growth, opportunities, major issues and challenges experienced by these enterprises. The data are collected mostly from secondary sources by way of access to various Government policies/ programs including published Annual Reports, Journals, Books and available official websites.

Literature Review

- Dr. M.S.Vasu, Dr. K. Jayachandra Growth and Development of MSMEs in India; Prospects & Problems.
- K, Vasanth, Majumdar M., K. Krishna (2012) in their paper have stated that since several successful models of the sustainable SME are gradually evolving, networks of SMEs would become essential for addressing the systemic problems under lying the industrial ecology, enterprise resilience, and global supply chain sustainability.
- Christopher J. Green, Colin H. Kirkpatrick, and Victor Murinde, (2006) in their paper have examined how financial sector development policy might contribute to poverty reduction, particularly by supporting the growth of micro and small enterprises (MSEs).

Role of MSME in India

MSME is under Ministry of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) headed by Honourable union minister Shri Kalraj Mishra. Working in tandem with the larger goal of pushing for economic growth, the implementation of many reforms made the SME/start-up space relatively bullish in 2016 but not necessarily elated. These include re-implementation of Public Procurement Policy, Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana, Make in India, Startup India, and Skill India. Aimed at increasing the growth of the manufacturing sector by 12-14% per annum and increase its share of GDP to 25% by 2025, the government plans to make financial and technical support more accessible.

Table Performance of MSME Sector in India

S.No.	Year	Total Working Enterprises	Employment Generated (In Lacs)	Market Values of Fixed Assets (Rs.in crores)
1	2007 – 08	361.76	805.23	868,546.79
2	2008– 09	377.36	842.00	920,459.84
3	2009 – 10	393.70	880.84	977,144.72
4	2010 – 11	410.80	921.79	1,038,546.08
5	2011 – 12	428.73	965.15	1,105,934.09
6	2012 – 13	447.64	1,011.69	1,182,757.64
7	2013 – 14	447.54	1,061.40	1,268,763.67
8	2014 – 15	488.46	1,114.29	1,363,700.54
9	2015 – 16	510.57	1,171.32	1,471,992.94

Sources: Annual Report of MSME, Government of India 2016 -2017.

Opportunities in MSME

The lack of access to new and better technology has prevented Indian MSMEs from growing at a rate that's equivalent to their potential. The Ministry of MSME may provide the following assistance to MSMEs for technology up-gradation.

Access to Foreign Technologies

Promote low-cost ICT solutions: the Ministry of MSMEs in India should facilitate MSMEs in procuring complete and low-cost ICT solutions to improve their capacity and productivity. awareness of these tools should also be increased among MSMEs.

Support for R&D

Provide opportunities for international partnership for industries and clusters where Indian MSMEs have an inherent competitive edge, the Ministry of MSME should create platforms through institutions like the NSIC and also form private partnerships to allow Indian MSMEs network with MSMEs abroad pp.

Create and Promote Innovation and R&D Culture

Government sector institutions that are at the cutting edge of research and innovation should be opened up for use by MSME innovators who are struggling to get funds and technology.

Assistance From Large Firms

Involve large enterprises in the development of MSME clusters: a long-term strategic plan should be implemented by the Ministry of MSME to facilitate and build long-term relationships with large enterprises and research supply institutes.

E-Governance & E-Procurement

E-governance and E-procurement, a must for easier compliance: online mechanisms should be provided to MSMEs to carry out all the necessary transactions for conducting business in the domestic and international markets. The government should also provide online access to rules and regulations, electronic methods for registration and electronic applications for government.

Government Initiatives

- Implementation of the Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises Development (“MSMED”) Act 2006 and Identifying existing and potential clusters.
- Providing strategic information such as benchmarking or trends.
- Boosting to investing in technology and infrastructure, Filling in investment gaps with FDI
- Linking firms to training programs from local universities and centers.
- It classifies industries based on the investment in plant & machinery, and not on turnover or employment, as is the case elsewhere.
- It defines the Indian SME segment at par with the existing concept of SMEs worldwide.
- As per its definition, an SME is an entity engaged in the production of goods and services involving investment from INR1 million to INR100 million in plant and machinery. The Small Industries Development Bank of India (“SIDBI”), **which is the main financial institute for the SME sector, plays a pivotal role. It is:**
- Responsible for the development of venture capital financing in the country to support the risk capital requirements of the sector.
- Investing in several venture capital funds for onward investments in the SME sector Some key funds, the SIDBI has invested in India leverage fund and India advantage fund.
- India development fund SMERA Initiatives To further streamline the process of SME financing, a dedicated rating agency called SME Rating Agency of India (“SMERA”) was launched by the SIDBI in association with some leading public and private sector banks of India, in 2005.

Issues and Challenges

The Committee on financial architecture of MSME sector in their Report submitted in February 2015 have identified some key issues¹⁶.

Some of the Major Challenges

Lack of Adequate Capital and Credit

The Report of the Working Group on Rehabilitation of sick MSMEs by the Reserve Bank of India has identified this situation as a crucial reason for the industrial sickness of this sector.

Poor and Inadequate Infrastructural Facilities

Deficiencies in the infrastructure and poor support facilities marked by inadequate access to basic facilities like water, power supply, road/rail connectivity, etc.

Inadequate Access and Marketing Linkages

Poor marketing linkages characterized by inadequate Government support and patronage, lack of adequate marketing infrastructure/ network facilities continue to be a greater challenge for marketing and sale of MSME products. In a non-cluster situation, these enterprises get segregated and are unable to ensure a reduction in procurement cost from big companies and fail to streamline the output-supply chain.

Lack of Skilled Human Resources

Non-availability of skilled workforce and better managerial/entrepreneurial expertise at the affordable cost near the location of enterprises is another such big challenge for the MSMEs in our country. Lack of managerial competence, the absence of proper training on resource planning and capital management, etc. hinders the growth of enterprises.

Lack of Access to New Technology

Most of the industries today require the application of advanced technology in their operations whereas in the Indian context continuance of low technology base results in low productivity by making these enterprises uncompetitive in the ever-widening market contexts.

Dilatory and Cumbersome Regulatory Practices

Cumbersome and dilatory regulatory clearances relating to sanction and disbursement of loans from commercial banks, collateral securities/guarantees, for construction permits, resolving insolvency and taxation, etc. continue to be the constraining factors for many MSMEs. No adherence to RBI guidelines regarding revival/rehabilitation of seeking enterprises by the Banks is another such constraint that needs to be addressed.

Suggestions

Easy Access to Finance and Credit

Institutional finance/credit from banks and other financing institutions should be promptly available without long and cumbersome procedures. Sanction of credit/loan applications by public sector banks should be made within a reasonable time frame at the affordable and reduced rate of interest.

Stepping up Infrastructural and Support Facilities

Deficiencies in basic infrastructural facilities like water, power supply, road/rail and telephone connectivity, etc. should be addressed on a priority basis. Use of solar or renewable energy as an alternative source should be encouraged in rural areas on a subsidized basis.

Creation of Adequate Marketing Linkages

For enhancing the sale of products, regular trade fairs/exhibitions, etc. should be conducted for the creation of a larger platform for better marketing facilities. The Govt. of India policy regarding 20% mandatory procurement of MSME products by government Departments/ State PSUs should be ensured.

Skill Development and Capacity Building

Initiatives should be taken for skill/competency development of human resources. Infrastructural and professional support from rural Self Employment Training Institutes (RSETI) Awareness / sensitization programmes and TV/Radio talks should be conducted.

Access to Modern Tools and Technology

Technological obsolescence should be replaced by the adoption of modern and latest tools and technology for increased productivity and quality product for competitive advantage.

Policy Intervention and Support Mechanisms

Industry-friendly policies should be initiated by the government for promoting infrastructural support facilities and for easy availability of finance by the scheduled banks. Government and Banks should take steps for revival of sick units as per RBI Guidelines and Credit Guarantee Fund Trust for Micro and Small Enterprises (CGAMSE) Scheme.

Conclusion

The Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise (MSMEs) are an important sector and plays a critical role in the Indian economy. MSMEs will continue to play a very important and vital role in our economy where the twin problems of unemployment and poverty constitute a major development challenge. There are several challenges in the sector of MSMEs. If the Government, Bank and Financial Institutions will take proper initiatives in the sector of MSME and they will take pride while servicing the MSMEs, these challenges can be solved and the economic growth rate of India will be 8-10% for the next decades.

MSMEs over the years have assumed greater significance in our burgeoning national economy by contributing to employment generation and rural industrialization. This sector possesses enough potential and possibilities to pushbutton accelerated industrial growth in our developing economy and well poised to support national programme like ‘Make in India.’

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